

Optimization of MIMO Antenna for 5G

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ABSTRACT

This Paper investigates the performance of MIMO Antenna for 5G applications. The antenna was designed using HFSS. The said size of the antenna was 1.2cm by 1.2cm. From the results it was observed that the antenna was optimized to frequency band of 3.5 GHz and 6.8 GHz, required for 5G band. The VSWR at the said bands are 1.4 and 1.8 respectively. Finally the measured gain is 2.366.

INTRODUCTION

As the number of users increases the frequency allocation becomes inadequate, because of the limited channel capacity. The number of users cannot go over a certain limit within the same frequency spectrum. Additionally, as the number of user's increases, co-channel interference also rises. Sending and receiving high-volume films on 3G (Third Generation) and 4G (Fourth Generation) frequency channels has become increasingly challenging for handheld devices

since the development of high definition (HD) and quadruple high definition (QHD) video standards. For high-quality multimedia to be transmitted and received wirelessly quickly across terminals, a larger bandwidth and a quicker data rate are therefore required [1]. To address this issue 5G frequencies are being researched because of their increased bandwidth. The introduction of 5G (Fifth Generation) technology is entering a revolutionary phase in wireless

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communication [2]. 5G is suitable for more users who need fast data rates since it offers more bandwidth and frequency channels than 3G and [1]. The main goals of 5G communication systems include high dependability, improved device-to-device communication, low latency (1 ms), greater flexibility, and data rate (up to 20 Gbit/s) and capacity. It is made to satisfy the growing needs for enormous machine-type communication, ultra-reliable low-latency communication, and faster data speeds [2-3]. 5G networks will combine low, mid, and high-frequency bands to offer a range of services with varying needs [4]. Considering its remarkable capabilities, 5G frequencies may have a low penetration power issue that causes the signal to weaken and fade away as it travels from transmitter to receiver with a single antenna at either end. Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) may be a preferable option for increasing the broadcast signal's range, particularly for small battery-operated devices in 1980, Arogyaswani Paulraj introduced MIMO. By using several antennas at the transmitter and receiver ends, MIMO technology improves spectral efficiency and system capacity, which is crucial for 5G [5]. Even so, its potential, problems like low gain and restricted bandwidth still exist, resulting in interference and less-than-ideal performance [6]. These problems require careful optimization of MIMO antenna systems to fully exploit their benefits. In order to optimize MIMO antennas, basic design elements like gain, bandwidth, and beamforming must be addressed. For better signal quality and less interference, higher gain antennas with directed beams and low side-lobe levels are essential. Wider bandwidth also guarantees effective use of the radio spectrum, which is a limited resource in contemporary communication systems. By directing energy toward targeted users, beamforming a crucial component of MIMO further improves system performance and makes efficient spatial multiplexing possible [5, 7]. The problem with the MIMO antenna arises due to low gain and limited bandwidth MIMO antenna gain can be increased by a wider bandwidth to minimize the interference. Therefore, to achieve high gain directional beams with low side loops and enable efficient

beam forming the optimization of MIMO antenna investigation is required.

ANTENNA DESIGN

The Figure 1 shows a flowchart outlining a process of Antenna design in HFSS as described below. Initially 60mm by 60mm antenna size is selected. The Fr4 was taken as substrate. The patch dimensions are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Outlining the process for the fabrication of proposed antenna

Figure 2 Implemented antenna in HFSS

RESULTS

RETURN LOSS

We could mention that the designed MIMO antenna providing us -13.7140 dB return loss at 3.5 GHz resonant frequency. It could be found from the complex conjugate curve, as shown in figure 4.1

Figure 3 Return loss vs frequency curve

We could also observed the bandwidth of designed antenna from figure 4.1. The calculation of bandwidth of MIMO antenna is given as

$$\text{Bandwidth} = f_h - f_l \quad (1)$$

Substituting the values of high frequency and low frequency in equation (1)

$$\text{Bandwidth} = (3.5413 - 3.4000) \text{ GHz}$$

$$\text{Bandwidth} = 0.1413 \text{ GHz} / 1800 \text{ MHz}$$

We could observed that the designed antenna providing bandwidth of 1800 MHz at resonant frequency 3.5GHz. Impedance bandwidth can be evaluated from reflection coefficient curve as follow:

VSWR

The VSWR of the rectangular MIMO antenna gives us 1.5. The value of VSWR is acceptable according to antenna theory. The simulated results of VSWR is shown in Figure 4

Figure 4 Simulated VSWR

GAIN OF ANTENNA:

The antenna possesses a maximum value of similarly the 3D-polar plot gave us the total gain of antenna which is 2.366

CONCLUSION

In modern world, 5G is a potent mobile and data communication technology. This Paper investigates the performance of MIMO Antenna for 5G applications. The antenna was designed using HFSS. The said size of the antenna was 1.2cm by 1.2cm. From the results it was observed that the antenna was optimized to frequency band of 3.5 GHz and 6.8 GHz, required for 5G band. The VSWR at the said bands are 1.4 and 1.8 respectively. Finally, the measured gain is 2.366

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